

FEATURES OF REHABILITATION MEASURES FOR MILITARY PERSONNEL WITH UPPER LIMB NERVE INJURIES

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the peculiarities of rehabilitation measures for upper limb nerve damage in the military. The authors note that rehabilitation should begin as early as possible, from the first days after the injury. The first period of rehabilitation, which lasts up to 6 months, focuses on immobilising the injured limb and preventing joint contractures. In the second period, which lasts up to 12 months, active rehabilitation begins, aimed at restoring joint mobility and muscle strength. In the third period, which lasts up to 18 months, rehabilitation is aimed at restoring limb function and returning the serviceman to military service.

The article describes the main rehabilitation methods used for upper limb nerve damage.

These include:

Immobilisation of the injured limb with plaster casts or external fixation devices. Passive and active-passive exercises to restore joint mobility. Active exercises to strengthen muscles. Electrical stimulation of muscles.

The authors of the article note that the effectiveness of rehabilitation depends on many factors, including the severity of the nerve damage, the timing of rehabilitation, and the individual characteristics of the soldier.

Keywords: rehabilitation, nerve damage, upper limbs, military personnel.

Introduction. The problem of rehabilitation of servicemen in Ukraine is extremely urgent. Since the beginning of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, which began on 24 February 2022, thousands of Ukrainian servicemen have been injured in combat zones, making every effort to preserve the territorial integrity of our country. The need for rehabilitation in Ukraine has increased significantly since the outbreak of war. Almost every medical facility needs qualified specialists in physical therapy to restore lost limb function after injuries, speed up recovery from surgery according to individual rehabilitation programmes that are drawn up by a physical therapist for each patient. In most cases, trauma, in particular to the upper extremities, occurs as a result of mine-blast injuries, shrapnel injuries, and gunshot wounds, which leads to complete or partial loss of arm function. Therefore, the work of a physical therapist with patients who have this type of injury is in demand and extremely important, as rehabilitation measures for military personnel are mandatory and necessary for their further successful integration into society and professional life. The purpose of the article.

The purpose of the article is to provide medical professionals with up-to-date information on the methods and timing of rehabilitation of servicemen who have suffered nerve damage to the upper extremities. This information will help to provide a general understanding of the problem and ensure effective rehabilitation of servicemen.

Rehabilitation for upper extremity nerve damage is a set of measures aimed at restoring limb functions that have been impaired as a result of injury. The patient's work with a physical therapist begins as early as possible, from the first days after the injury.

The first period of rehabilitation focuses on immobilising the injured limb and preventing joint contractures. Immobilisation can be carried out using plas-

ter casts, orthoses or external fixation devices. It is necessary to protect the limb from additional injuries and prevent its deformation.

Prevention of joint contractures

Joint contractures are pathological changes that lead to restricted joint mobility. They can occur as a result of damage to the nerves of the hand if no preventive measures are taken. Passive and active-passive exercises are used to prevent joint contractures. Passive exercises are performed by a rehabilitation therapist or by the patient with the help of someone else. Active-passive exercises are performed by the patient with the help of a physical therapist. For example, flexion and extension of the forearm, hand, and fingers by the patient directly by the physical therapist are all examples of passive exercises to prevent contractures. The tasks of the first period of rehabilitation of a patient with this type of disease are:

- immobilise the affected limb -prevent contractures of the damaged limb by prescribing passive and active-passive exercises.

In order for rehabilitation to start effectively and bring positive results, the physical therapist must assess the patient's level of pain sensitivity, as it is known that pain during rehabilitation sessions can exhaust the patient and slow down the recovery process. The physical therapist should monitor the pain sensitivity during exercise, and if the patient experiences severe pain during exercise, the exercise should be performed until the pain is no longer felt.

Positioning and arm orthosis are among the most important aspects of rehabilitation for patients with upper extremity nerve damage. These methods are used to ensure that the injured arm is fixed in the most optimal position to reduce pain and prevent re-injury.

An orthosis is a rigid support device that is made individually for each patient; it can be plastic, metal or plaster. They are used to protect, support and immobilise the limbs. If the patient's injured arm is left in an

arbitrary position and not fixed, this can lead to compensatory movements of the limb, an even greater load on the affected muscles, stretching of the affected nerves, long-term swelling, constant pain, and, as a result, a slower recovery process.

The second rehabilitation period for nerve damage to the arm lasts up to 12 months.

During this period, active rehabilitation begins, aimed at restoring joint mobility and muscle strength. Active exercises

Active exercises are performed by the patient independently. They are aimed at strengthening muscles and restoring joint mobility.

Examples of active exercises:

- Flexion and extension of the fingers.
- Flexion and extension of the hand.
- Flexion and extension of the forearm.
- Flexion and extension of the shoulder.

You should also include flexion and extension of the shoulder, forearm, and hands; abduction, extension, raising and lowering of the arms alternately.

Physiotherapy.

Electrical muscle stimulation

Electrical muscle stimulation is a method used to increase muscle contraction by applying an electric current.

Electrical muscle stimulation can be used both in combination with active exercise and independently.

Balneotherapy is a method used to restore limb function using mineral waters, therapeutic baths and mud.

Balneotherapy can be used both in combination with active exercises in water and electrical stimulation, and independently.

Tasks of the second rehabilitation period:

- Restore mobility of the hand joints.
- Strengthen the muscles of the arm.

Exercise should be done regularly, several times a day.

Massage is also an effective method of rehabilitation in the second period. It is an effective method of rehabilitation for nerve damage in the hand. It helps to improve blood circulation and microcirculation in tissues, reduce swelling and inflammation, and relieve muscle spasms. The massage technique for hand nerve damage should be gentle. The masseur should use light movements, avoiding strong pressure. The duration of massage for arm nerve damage is from 15 to 30 minutes. Massage should be performed several times a week.

Materials and methods.

The study examined 12 patients with various types of upper limb injuries who were treated in the therapeutic and neurological departments of Ternopil City Municipal Hospital No. 3. 100% of the surveyed patients were men aged 22 to 59 years, 100% of the surveyed patients served in various military units at the time of injury and sustained upper limb injuries while performing military missions in the eastern regions of our country where active hostilities are taking place. We tested the sensitivity of both upper extremities with a needle, while the patients' eyes were closed, so that by tingling the needle on the skin surface of the healthy and injured

arm, we asked about the sensations, whether the tingling felt "sharp", "dull" or absent, and found out whether the sensations were different on the healthy and injured limb or felt the same.

A visual analogue pain scale was used. This is a linear scale on which the patient marked the location of his pain level on a horizontal line 10 cm long, one end meaning "no pain", the other end meaning "the worst possible pain".

Manual muscle testing of the upper limb muscles was performed to assess their strength. Namely: MMT of the biceps brachii, triceps brachii, radial extensors of the hand and posterior interosseous muscles.

The assessment is based on a 5-point scale:

0 points - complete absence of visible or palpable muscle contraction;

1 point - muscle contraction, but without movement;

2 points - movement performed in full amplitude without gravity and resistance;

3 points - full contraction and movement of the muscle with resistance;

4 points - the patient is able to overcome moderate resistance from the therapist;

5 points - the patient can overcome maximum resistance.

We checked deep reflexes on the upper limbs:

Carpal radial reflex: examined from the periosteum, when the neurological hammer hits the cubital process, flexion, pronation of the hand and possible flexion of the fingers are normal. The test is performed symmetrically on both sides.

The flexor-extensor reflex is triggered by hitting the biceps tendon with a neurological hammer. When the tendon is struck, the arm bends at the elbow. Check on both sides.

Extensor-ulnar reflex. The triceps tendon is examined. When the tendon is struck, the arm extends in the elbow joint. We compare on both sides.

Research results

The results of our study indicate that among the 12 patients studied, all were male (100%). All 12 were injured during combat missions (100%), and each of them was in the eastern region of our country, namely Donetsk region (100%), at the time of injury.

When checking pain sensitivity, all 12 patients, given the complexity of their injuries, have pain (100%) of varying intensity, according to the nature of the injury: 7 patients (58.3%) have gunshot wounds, 3 patients (25%) have shrapnel wounds, and 2 patients (16.6%) have mine-blast wounds. In terms of segmental injuries, 6 patients have humerus injuries (50%), 4 people have forearm injuries (33.3%), and 2 wounded have injured hands (16.6%). Also, among the patients, 3 men have radial nerve damage to the left limb (16.6%).

It should also be remembered that servicemen often need psychological support and recovery after being injured in combat zones.

Psychological recovery of servicemen is an important stage of rehabilitation. It is aimed at coping with the consequences of trauma, adapting to a new life and returning to normal functioning in society.

Trauma can have a significant impact on the mental state of a soldier. It can cause psychological problems such as:

- Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) is the most common mental disorder that occurs after a trauma. It is characterised by symptoms such as:
 - Recurrent memories of trauma
 - Avoiding places, people or situations that remind you of the trauma.
 - A constant feeling of anxiety and tension.
 - Problems with sleep.
 - Loss of interest in ordinary activities
- Depression is a condition characterised by anxiety, depressed mood, loss of interest in normal activities and other symptoms.
- Anxiety disorders are conditions characterised by increased levels of anxiety and fear.

When working with military personnel, it is extremely important to be tactful, listen and ensure a favourable attitude, be a kind of empath, so that the patient sees you as a person who understands their problem, empathises with them and is ready to help; motivate them to work hard to improve their health, both physical and moral. In today's harsh realities of life, physical therapists play an important role in restoring the health and functionality of patients, including

military personnel. They need to have the right knowledge, skills and qualities to provide the best possible treatment, as this is more important than ever for our country. Physical therapy is an integral part of our country's recovery in such turbulent and challenging times.

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